

Influence of Alkali on Zeolite Modification I. Zeolite 13 X*

P. C. BORTHAKUR, G. C. BHATTACHARYA, M. C. UPRETI and S. N. DUTTA

Regional Research Laboratory, Jorhat, Assam

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The effect on the thermochemical properties of zeolite 13 X on prolonged contact with alkaline solution has been studied. Solubility of zeolite 13 X is quite small in 2N alkali, but change in chemical composition with decrease of $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ ratio and increase of cation content was observed due to preferential dissolution of silica from zeolite. The zeolite does not undergo structural change but becomes contaminated with other aluminosilicate material formed due to recombination of aluminate and silicate ions in solution.

THE synthesis of zeolites including zeolite X and Y which are isostructural with the naturally occurring zeolites faujasite are normally done at 80-100° from crystallization of alkali aluminosilicate hydrogel in alkaline medium. The composition of zeolite X has been reported to vary depending upon the conditions and methods of synthesis¹. The variation of framework composition lead into change of their characteristic properties like thermal stability, surface area, adsorption characteristics, etc., which determine their suitability as adsorbents and catalysts. Normally with increase of silica/alumina ratio the sorptive capacity as well as thermal stability of faujasite type zeolite increases. Kuhl et al reported that the silica/alumina ratio of these zeolites can also be increased by leaching some of the alumina with weak acids like ethylene diamine tetraacetic acid⁴.

The concentration of alkali used in the crystallization process has certain effect in the crystallization process and in the nature of the crystals. In high alkaline medium, sodium aluminosilicate hydrogel gives the feldspathoid hydroxysodalite in place of zeolite^{5,6}. Under alkali concentration inhibiting formation of hydroxysodalite, it has been reported that increase of alkali concentration increases the rate of crystallization and decreases the size of the crystals of a particular zeolite^{6,7}. Furthermore it has been shown that in a given system prolongation of crystallization period may lead into reconversion of a metastable zeolite phase into another more stable phase. In sodium aluminosilica hydrogel system, reconversion of zeolite X→P, has been reported by a number of workers^{8,9}. The effect of alkali (caustic soda) on the structure, composition and thermal properties of zeolite X is investigated in the present study. The concentration of alkali is so chosen that hydroxysodalite is not formed.

Experimental

(a) *Materials*: Linde 13 X molecular sieve in powder form are taken. Sodium hydroxide used was analar grade (B.D.H).

(b) *Analysis*: The SiO_2 , Al_2O_3 are estimated gravimetrically by standard procedure. Powder X-ray diffraction patterns were taken in a Radon X-ray generator using iron filtered Co K_α radiation. The thermal characteristics were determined in a MOM derivatograph^{10,11}. Simultaneous thermogravimetry (tg), differential thermogravimetry (dtg) and differential thermal analysis (dta) were recorded using α -alumina calcined at 1200° as the reference material as well as diluent. The thermal characteristics of all the samples were recorded maintaining identical instrumental conditions.

(c) *Procedure*: Equal amount (10 g) of fully hydrated molecular sieve zeolites are put in different conical flasks. To each of the flasks 50 ml of 2N caustic soda solution was slowly added and then the mixture was refluxed at water bath temperature for 4 hour, 8 hour and 12 hour. The contents were then filtered, washed thoroughly with distilled water and then dried in air oven at 100°. The dried materials were kept in 100% humidity and then examined by X-ray. The thermal characteristics and silica, alumina content of the solids were also determined. The silica and alumina content of the mother liquor and washing were also examined.

Results and Discussion

X-ray powder diffraction data for original 13 X and 13 X after 12 hour alkali treatment are presented in Table 1. Diffraction patterns of 4 hour and 8 hour treated samples were found to be exactly similar to the original untreated zeolite. The diffraction pattern of 12 hour treated samples, though similar to that of the original untreated zeolite, showed general decrease in intensity of the whole pattern and slight broadening of lines in the low angle region.

The dta and tg curves of alkali treated alongwith the original zeolite samples are shown in Figs. 1 and 2 respectively. Weight loss was calculated

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TABLE 1—X-RAY POWDER DIFFRACTION DATA

13 X untreated		13 X after 12 hour alkali treatment	
14.18	(s)	14.18	(s)
8.76	(m)	8.76	(<m)
7.45	(m ⁺)	7.45	(<m ⁻)
5.71	(m ⁻)	5.71	(<m ⁺)
4.79	(w ⁺)	4.79	(w)
4.37	(m ⁻)	4.37	(w ⁺)
4.18	(vvw)	4.18	(vvw)
3.97	(vw)	3.97	(vvw)
3.80	(m ⁺⁺)	3.80	(m ⁺⁺)
3.34	(m ⁺⁺)	3.34	(<m ⁺⁺)
3.06	(w)	3.06	(w ⁻)
2.94	(w ⁺)	2.94	(w ⁻)
2.86	(m ⁺⁺)	2.86	(<m ⁺⁺)
2.79	(w ⁺)	2.79	(w)
2.74	(vvw)	2.74	(vvw)
2.67	(m ⁻)	2.67	(<m ⁻)
2.62	(w)	2.62	(vw)
2.57	(w ⁻)	2.57	(vvw)
2.41	(w ⁺)	2.41	(w)
2.26	(vw)	2.26	(vvw)
2.22	(w)	2.22	(w)
2.18	(w)	2.18	(w)

s=strong, w=weak, m=medium.

Fig. 1 Differential Thermal Analysis of Zeolite 13 X.
(1) : original, (2) : 4 hr treated, (3) : 8 hr treated,
(4) : 12 hr treated

from the tg curves. The original and treated zeolites as well as the respective mother liquors were analysed for silica and alumina to determine their $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ ratios. The results are presented in Table 2.

In conformity to the composition of the solids, the mother liquors become rich in silica with time, indicating preferential leaching of silica which may be due to higher acidity of silica in comparison to

Fig. 2. Thermogravimetry Curves of Zeolite 13 X.

(1) : original, (2) : 4 hr treated, (3) : 8 hr treated,
(4) : 12 hr treated.

TABLE 2—VARIATION IN $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ MOLE RATIO AND PERCENT WEIGHT LOSS

Sample	$\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ in solid	$\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ in mother liquor	Al_2O_3 moles in mother liquor	Wt. loss %
Original zeolite	2.46	—	—	23.6
4 hr treated	2.39	12.35	7.827×10^{-6}	25.0
8 hr treated	2.37	48.01	0.078×10^{-6}	26.0
12 hr treated	2.33	66.92	0.079×10^{-6}	25.5

alumina. The amount of alumina in the mother liquors is found to decrease with time. If the alumina in the mother liquor is accounted for the dissolution of the sieve in alkali, the solubility of the zeolite is found to decrease with time. Taking the unit cell composition of Linde 13 X as $\text{Na}_{86}[(\text{AlO}_2)_{86}(\text{SiO}_2)_{106}] 276 \text{H}_2\text{O}$, on the basis of aluminium content the solubility of the zeolite 13 X in 4 hour in 2N alkali would be less than 0.6706 g/liter. The decrease of aluminium content in the mother liquor indicates some reaction between the sodium aluminate and sodium silicate with subsequent formation of solid product. The decrease in intensity of the powder diffraction pattern of 12 hour treated sample is thus attributed to decrease in the quantity of 13 X due to contamination of zeolite with some amorphous material. The broadening of the lines indicates a variation of $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ ratio of the treated sample in comparison to original 13 X.

The general nature of the DTA curves of original as well as treated samples as shown in Fig. 1, is same. All are characterised by low temperature large endothermic peak, due to removal of zeolitic

water, followed by a small endothermic peak and high temperature exothermic peaks due to structural breakdown and recrystallization. The curves exhibit some change of the temperature range of the low temperature endotherm and in the number and temperature range of the exotherms. In case of the original untreated zeolite, the peak temperature for the removal of zeolitic water lies around 195° and for 12 hour treated sample, it lies around 220°. The small endothermic peak as observed in the original 13 X around 405°, however, is not affected by alkali treatment. The original 13 X exhibits two exotherms, maximum corresponding respectively to around 800° and 935°. The 4 and 8 hour treated sample also exhibits two exotherms, maximum in the first sample lies around 795° and 920° and in the second sample it lies around 820° and 930° respectively, whereas the 12 hour treated sample exhibits three exotherms, peak temperature corresponding around 800°, 905° and 955° respectively.

All the alkali treated zeolites, though possessing different $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ ratio, exhibit the first exotherm at about 800° and show the same degree of crystallinity as determined by X-ray analysis. It can thus be concluded that slight variation in composition of zeolite 13 X (change in $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ ratio) does not affect either its thermal stability or crystallinity. However, why the 8 hour treated sample, incidently possessing maximum water adsorption capacity of 26% and intermediate $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ ratio than the other treated samples is thermally more stable could not be explained. The appearance of an additional high temperature exotherm in case of 12 hour treated sample also indicates that it is contaminated with some other material. This supports the earlier conclusion that the silica and alumina that dissolve in alkali react in alkaline medium with subsequent reprecipitation.

The increase of peak temperature with increase of contact time of the zeolite with the alkali indicates that the bonding of water in the zeolite framework becomes stronger with contact time. The bonding of water in a particular zeolite framework depends on the type and sizes of canals and cavities in the zeolite and more particularly on the nature of the cation and their distribution in the framework^{1,8}. The removal of water from zeolite framework requires energy sufficient to overcome the attractive forces between the water molecules and the cations and would naturally increase with the increase of cation density in zeolite. The preferential removal of silica from the zeolite by the

alkali, increases its aluminium content as a result of which the number of cations needed to compensate the extra charge of AlO_4^- tetrahedra will increase. Slight increase in the weight loss and change observed in the nature of endothermic peaks may thus be accounted for this increase in cation content due to alkali treatment.

Conclusion :

The solubility of zeolite 13 X is quite small in 2N alkali, but there is preferential dissolution of silica from zeolite leading to change in chemical composition with decrease of $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ ratio and increase of cation content. On prolonged contact with alkali, the product does not undergo structural change, but becomes contaminated with other aluminosilicate material formed due to recombination of aluminate and silicate ions in solution. Hence the composition of the crystals formed at different times, during synthesis, would not be the same; crystals formed initially possessing maximum $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ ratio and minimum cation content.

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